

*Smart system of renewable energy storage based on **IN**tegrated **EV**s and **bA**tteries to empower mobile, **D**istributed and centralised **E**nergy storage in the distribution grid*

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interfaces
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
GFO	Global Flexibility Operator
SOTA	State of The Art
TSO	Transmission System Operator
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EV	Electric Vehicle
QM	Quality Management
ESB	Energy Service Broker
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
ESP	Energy Service Provider
HAS	Home Automation Service
ESCO	Energy Service Company
BRP	Balancing Responsible Party
ESB	Energy Service Broker
OTT	Over the Top (Internet distribution)
FO	Flexibility Operator
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
CPU	Central Processing Unit
ToU	Time of Use
BM	Business model
PBBM	Platform-Based Business Model
IIP	Integrated INVADE Platform
AMS	Advanced Metering System
EUG	Exploitation User Group
CES	Centralized Energy Storage
DES	Distributed Energy Storages
OCPI	Open Charge Point Interface

1 Executive summary

The business model work in the INVADE project has followed four distinct phases: exploration, development, validation and exploitation. This report is the result of the validation part, but also covers the business model part of the exploitation work which mainly was done in WP3, in particular D3.6.

During the last year of the project we have seen evidence of Platform-Based Business Models (PBBM) companies appearing in the European market. These companies are coming from the ICT domain, but also hold strong energy competence. So far, they are small, but fast growing.

Also, some selected academic papers are describing the relevance of platform-based business models in the energy market and are pointing both at the flexibility and EV-charging markets as two of the most relevant areas for PBBM.

The feedback we have got from the Exploitation User Group (EUG) confirms to a great extent that PBBMs are highly relevant in the future energy market. But the generic business model framework is quite abstract, so it needs to be combined with the more concrete business canvas tool to provide value. So, for high level strategic discussions regarding market positioning and the company's new role and direction, the framework is a good tool. But for drilling down in concrete customer value propositions and more, the business canvas tool is important. When it comes to the concept of V2X, the EUG is sceptical to whether this service will have a profound impact in the future energy market.

The external stakeholder group was a bit more sceptical towards the PBBM. The main arguments against this business model was that becoming a dominant platform actor is hard. Also, as the energy market is highly regulated, this market is harder to enter. This is a valid argument, but we will argue that as this is true for the grid part, it is not true behind the meter. And this is exactly where the platform-based business models flourish.

The external stakeholders were also shown the concept of flexibility operator (FO), and they all acknowledged this role and concept. Those contributing in WP9 believe that the FO role will naturally be divided into a local and global role, where the local flexibility role will not be regulated at all, whereas the more dominant global flexibility role has a higher probability to become regulated or neutral.

When it comes to the PBBM validation in the different pilots, we see that not all the pilots are ideal for applying a PBBM. The pilots that already have a local ecosystem with existing services towards prosumer/consumers and have prepared for energy-IoT control for

customers (like Greenflux and Smartly) are ideally positioned to apply PBBM and to take on the local flexibility role.

Pilot owners that are not focusing on the end-user flexibility services and thus prosumers/consumers (like Estabanel) are not ideal for platform-based business models. We believe this has to do with the fact that PBBM depends on sourcing first, and exploits digital technologies like IoT, AI and Internet distribution to succeed.

But in between these two extremes, we find the two remaining pilots. We have chosen to call them hybrids, because they have this feature but in different forms.

Looking at the German pilot, we find an exciting combination of a utility company Badenova and the platform-based company SMA. Here they join forces to be able to help the DSO to avoid high fines for exceeding its predicted max peak load for the entire electrical grid in the city. And they do this by joining forces with SMA who controls energy IoT units at the customer side and allowing for the INVADE platform to send additional control signals. So, a hybrid of industrial actors.

The Bulgarian pilot on the other side, can also be characterized as a hybrid, but this time as a hybrid of tangible and in-tangible (ICT-based) flexibility services. Albena's core service is sustainable accommodation and tourism. And they had already many sustainable initiatives like up-cycling of waste, forest protection and more. Now, with the INVADE project they combine this with increasing the production of renewable energy and controlling load balancing using a battery as well as water boilers that are upgraded to IoT units capable to execute control signals from the Invade platform. Thus, they now have a hybrid ecosystem of tangible and ICT/IoT based sustainable/renewable services which is unique in the European accommodation/tourism market.

We see a clear pattern related to market entry for flexibility. The recommended order should be:

1. Start with a core service that enables control of the flexibility sources like smart EV-chargers, PV, smart home, batteries, thermal heaters.
2. Then enter the most mature market first where we find effect-based tariffs, typically medium to large companies and multi-tenant buildings. And introduce end-user flexibility services. Here, financing from the local ecosystem can accelerate sourcing.
3. Do industrial shifts towards neighbouring markets/branches to increase sourcing.
4. Start doing up-stream flexibility trading and aggregation when regulation allows DSOs to participate.

The flexibility role will typically be divided between two main entities; the local flexibility operator controlling energy-IoT assets and end customers, and the global flexibility operator doing the more difficult trading and market place for flexibility. Simplification for end-customers should be a big part of the value proposition, and simplification can range from user interaction over billing to reducing the number of gateways/apps. The aim should be to remove customer pain points.

The global flexibility operator should start in national markets where regulatory barriers for the DSOs are removed first. Today, the regulation for DSOs favours investing in new infrastructure only, and not flexibility trading. This must be changed for an upstream market to be established.

Despite a dramatic drop in price of batteries, all the pilots claim that a one-service approach is not feasible. You will need to stack more services on a battery. An example is peak shaving for EVs, emergency function and increased self-consumption at the customer side.

We see that the INVADE business model framework support the idea of a global consolidating role of DSOs and local ecosystems, thus becoming one column in EUs Digital Single Market for big data. The global flexibility role is yet to be taken. However, taking this platform position will require investments at a level we rarely see in Europe today. This is an important part of the reason why US and Asia based companies are taking these global positions in other industries. And as the platform-based business models have an inherent feature of “the winner takes it all”, it is advisable that the European Commission ceases this chance to conquer this global market position as part of its journey towards EUs Digital Single Market for Big Data.

2 Introduction

The impact of new business models in industries can be profound. And traditional markets are particularly vulnerable in times when regulation is changing. For this reason, this report is targeted towards companies that are already in the energy market or are considering entering this market.

The report will shed light on how platform-based business models (PBBM) can be utilized in an energy market, and how our developed business model framework from D9.4 fits with reality in the INVADE pilot companies, exploitation cases and in the energy market in general.

Readers of this report should have a clear understanding of which role to seek, how to create and capture value, and what the revenue streams could be.

For the European Commission, understanding how new, innovative and sustainable business models work, and how they can change the business landscape is important. Can these business models scale, and will there be a need for new regulation are examples of questions to be looked into.

The report defines the final deliverable from Work Package 9 on business models and energy market structures. The ambition is thus to make an effort in answering the questions that the original project proposal raised. This report also attempts to close open-ended discussions in former WP9 deliverables related to the work package's primary objective. This objective has been *to develop innovative business models for energy storage in distribution networks in order to maximise impact of the INVADE project*. An inherent part of this has been to explore and understand existing business models in the field and their structure.

A major part of this was undertaken early in the project and presented in the deliverable D9.1. This was further followed up through subsequent efforts leading to the main theoretical framework presented in deliverable D9.4. A platform-based business model has been introduced to substantiate the role of a Flexibility Operator (FO) and to assure maximum value capture for this role. The FO role was introduced at the inception of the project as a market entity that would be able to consolidate flexible energy resources and aggregate this for the benefit of the grid and the energy market. Notably the principal resources specifically addressed in the INVADE project has been batteries, flexible loads and electric vehicles (battery on wheels). During the course of the project surveys of the market and parallel domains suggested that control of the resources could be both direct and indirect. Local control implied real-time monitoring and control, while indirect control relayed signals from a more central point to the local control. In fact, it was observed that multiple and distributed control units at a local level could all be coordinated from one central point. Hence, constituting a basis for an ecosystem connected by means of the INVADE platform. This idea was the main contribution of the deliverable D9.4.

This also defined the basis for the approach documented here where the stakeholders connected to the INVADE platform and thus an emerging ecosystem have been investigated. Value creation, business propositions, risks, critical resources, cost structures and soft factors related to end-user engagement and preferences, have all been embraced by this. An important input has been the experimental work that has been going on in the pilots, organized and documented in Work Package 10. In turn, this has defined an important basis for the business cases and exploitation activities organized by Work Package 3.

It is a logical consequence that this report should be of specific interest to the stakeholders that could interact across the INVADE platform and co-create value for all parties involved and

the assets connected. Such an audience would include business developers and managers in enterprises pursuing the FO role and other positions within the ecosystem that the FO could organize. Battery owners, charging point operators, utilities and grid owners, retailers, Energy Service Companies (ESCO) and aggregators and end-users or their facilitators are all members of the principal group that we want to address with this report. We identify roles that could be adopted to harness existing value creation and add new revenue streams in a system where batteries and other flexibility resources make a difference. These roles embrace and cultivate new services that could represent spin-out possibilities or be integrated with existing operations.

We think too, that European regulators and policy makers should be aware of the possibilities that the work in WP9 has unveiled. In this report we conclude, beyond doubt, that present regulations and policies in European countries represent a hurdle for stakeholders that want to capture the full value of consolidated battery services, smart charging of vehicles and demand-response programs associated with these. This raises a concern as we observe that this reduces the desired societal, environmental and business impact that could otherwise be achieved. In fact, cooperation across different work packages, notably WP3 on exploitation and business development and WP2 on dissemination, suggests that Europe in many ways could be giving away the initiative to non-European interests. Navigant Research [1] recently published work on microgrids which use renewable energy resources and battery storage as the primary source of energy supply and support. The investment rate on all continents has surged during the last years, while the situation in Europe is stagnant. Another target for this report is the work that is undertaken by the EU Commission itself. The BRIDGE is an obvious channel for the findings that we report. Of particular importance is INVADE's and WP9's answer to the recent "Clean Energy for All European Citizens" package [1] published this year by the Commission.

3 Problem formulation

3.1 Background

In trying to meet the primary objective in WP9 and pursue novel business models for energy storage in distribution networks we hypothesized that flexibility assets and stakeholders controlling these could be organized in a non-linear way where transactions could be bi-directional. The reason for this is that entities such as prosumers and battery owners have dual interests, sometimes being a buyer and sometimes being a supplier. Drivers of EVs could

be charged for charging the battery of their car, but earn credits too by taking part in a smart charging regime that requires extensive flexibility on the driver's account. We collected market intelligence to support this view and studied established successful enterprises that have adopted such business models. Our initial work on this was also published [3]. A more extensive deliberation on the potential efficacy of this theoretical framework was further developed and presented in deliverable D9.4 [4]. The overall concept that was introduced here has been depicted in Figure 1. It illustrates a very generic ecosystem that link different assets for mutual benefits. As with all ecosystems a key element is the symbiotic mechanisms that define it. In business terms this implies shared

Figure 1: Generic ecosystem as described in D9.4

economy effects, back-to-back utilization of resources, non-linear revenue streams, reinforcement and multiplication effects, all which can be encapsulated within the framework of a platform based business model [5 = Parker]. A platform based business model operating in a smart grid environment would, as a natural consequence rely on and prosper on data exchanges. The whole concept related to management and operation of batteries, loads and chargers include sensor and effectors that involve extensive volumes of data. Cultivation and analysis of data harvests represent part of the total value capture. Feeds of raw data that are directed one way as well as refined and aggregated results going the opposite way constitute part of the dual value capture between stakeholders in the ecosystem that was presented in D9.4. Figure 2 presents an abstract view of this.

SBL= Service Business Logic (value added algorithm, customer service etc)

Figure 2: An abstract view of the value capture as presented in D9.4

What D9.4 did not substantiate were underlying elements contributing to the value capture shown in Figure 2. However, work in D9.4 were related to the use cases defined in WP4. These use cases defined the value creating services that batteries and other flexibility resources could leverage through the technical and business related work taking place in the INVADE project.

The WP10 related work in defining Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for the five pilots in the project were instrumental too. Some of the KPIs that have been defined stemmed from the endeavors in WP9 and WP3 were the idea was to determine absolute or relative performance for the pilots compared to traditional measures of managing flexibility. The purpose has thus simply been to define a goal for the work in the pilots to determine what could be a tipping point for future exploitation of the results generated. That would also be a mark for value capture and of significant relevance to the work associated with this report.

3.2 From Deliverable 9.4

The work on Deliverable 9.4 hypothesized how new business models can enter and be exploited in a service driven energy market. New insights were developed but left several questions unanswered. Some of the unanswered questions and open-ended issues are listed below. On a general scale we found that traditional canvas methods could not support all aspects among platform and ecosystem-based business models. Yet, we have used this as a basis for all the work reported here. Beyond this we made the following reflections:

- Not all platform-based business models are successful, and some struggle with growth and/or profits. So, what are the factors that one should be aware of to avoid the pains?
- Are there more supportive cases that could guide the ongoing effort for the type of business models that promise to leverage the work that is defined and tested in the project?
- Can the business models that we are pursuing better incorporate social responsibility and combine findings from pilots with broader concepts of social and environmental sustainability in addition to economic and financial concerns as discussed in deliverable D3.4?
- Can we substantiate the role of the flexibility operator (FO) through the definition of concrete business cases? To better dissect this role would help to understand how different flexibility services could be organized, stacked and delivered for to optimize value capture.

3.3 Final questions to be answered

With the background and previous work referenced above, this report attempts to answer a series of research questions that was raised at the outset of the project or emerged as a result of the work undertaken in the project. These research questions have been listed below:

1. The platform-based business model and the ecosystem is one answer to the rich framework of business models heralded in the original project proposal. The pivotal role in this framework is the Flexibility Operator (FO) that offers, mitigates and relays a rich set of services based on batteries, smart charging, V2G/B/X and demand-response. The platform defines a number of relationships between stakeholders and potential transactions between these. Two-way dependencies and flow of data are essential in order to define a platform-based business model framework like the one that has been proposed. From this follows:
2. Are there sufficient findings and evidence in the project to conclude that this is true?
3. Is the business model framework conjectured suitable for the type of stakeholders that have been addressed in the project and partly tested in the pilots?
4. How can stakeholders really benefit from being part of the ecosystem that the platform model endeavours to organize and what evidence has been found to support this?

From this follows the question, does INVADE offer an effective business tool to solve problems for prosumers, BRPs, DSOs?

5. How does the business model framework developed create space for new technological players and roles specialising in energy storage so that they can acquire a profitable operation?
6. In what way does the platform-based business model framework and the Flexibility Operator encourage active consumer participation in flexibility management while respecting their consumption preferences and behaviour patterns?
7. Can the business model framework tread the fine line between maximizing profits for stakeholders while optimizing social welfare?
8. Are there obstacles that need to be removed in order to harness the suggested platform-based business model concept?
9. In what way should regulations and policies for the European energy storage market be changed seen from the point of view of business model realization?
10. Will the framework defined and the business models developed in this project be able to create space for new technological players and roles specialising in energy storage and provide a framework for their profitable operation in the distribution grid?
11. At the inception of the project, multi-dimensional value of storage rather than cost of storage was seen as a likely priority. Can services be stacked to aggregate revenues and how can this yield interesting profits or other gains for those involved?
12. Do the business models presented in D9.4 allow to reach the large-scale impact promised in the DoA?

It is thus the objective of this report to answer as many of these questions as possible and make recommendations along the same lines to promote the use of the findings described.

4 State-of-the-art update

The first deliverable in WP9 was the state-of-the-art review of new business models in the energy market. This chapter will not repeat this effort, and as Deliverable D9.6 focuses on validation, the update will use new examples and findings from the industry and academic research. Thus, this chapter is an update, not a new state of the art analysis.

We will concentrate on two examples from the Norwegian and German energy market, and one academic paper from Cambridge University specifically addressing application of platform-based business models in the energy market.

4.1 Tibber and Fresh Energy

The new energy service companies Tibber and Fresh Energy have a lot in common. Tibber is located in Norway, and Fresh Energy is a spinout of RWE in Germany. They can both fit into the INVADE business model framework, but we have chosen to focus on Tibber. The reason for this is two-fold:

- Tibber has an even leaner approach to Advanced Metering Systems (AMS), as all the Norwegian DSOs now have completed the AMS rollout. And as every meter has a HAN-port that can provide real time consumption/production data¹, they have a much lower cost using a HAN-port reader compared to Fresh Energy which must do the costly AMS installation themselves. Tibber's HAN-reader is a do-it-yourself product.
- Tibber has been in the market for longer and has a more comprehensive ecosystem.

So, for the rest of this chapter, the analysis will focus on Tibber.

4.1.1 Mapping to the INVADE business model framework

Tibber is an excellent example of a value network, and despite its young age, the ecosystem is comprehensive. We have sorted their ecosystem into three distinct categories; smart home services, smart energy services and EV-charging services.

The mapping is based on studies and can contain some minor errors, but the overall picture is clear. Due to space limitations, not all of their ecosystem-partners are shown in the figure. One example is Ngenic which also provides their own gateway and provides smart waterborne heat services. Another is Heatfit that is an ecosystem partner of Futurehome providing smart thermostats.

¹ This is due to a four-quadrant meter measuring two-way flow of both active and reactive energy.

It is also worth noting that some of Tibber’s services are fully/direct integrated into their ecosystem (and app), whereas others are indirectly integrated via a third-party service provider like Futurehome.

They also have a substantial list of global service providers in their local ecosystem.

Figure 3 Mapping of Tibber into the Invade business model framework

4.1.2 Description of value creation, stakeholders and value capture in the ecosystem

Value creation is happening both at the ecosystem partners as well as within Tibber. Even the customers create value by providing usage data to train Tibber’s algorithms, and they also create value for Tibber via the network effect (aggregating volume) in energy trading.

Tibber mainly creates value in three areas:

1. Simplification. Just by looking at the mapping, we see that Tibber simplifies the energy life of many different user groups (EV car owners), thus also extending the market reach. The app itself also provides informative graphics and clear savings information,

so the customers no longer must search for these numbers. Collecting the services in just one app is also simplification for the end-customer.

2. New services. Tibber is converting electricity from an invisible product to visible services. This is achieved using exclusive hardware (HAN reader) which is their own property, to collect the real-time metering values for the household. So far their partner Easee provides load balancing services for EV-owners in combination with Tibber's HAN reader (Pulse), and this is the flexibility service offered as of today. And as described in D9.4, this is a feature or add-on service, not the core product.
3. AI, analytics, trading robots. These tools create value for Tibber by enabling Tibber to get the best electricity prices in the spot market. This is referred to as "same-side network externalities" in [17]. For the end-customers this is reflected in price guaranties if they choose to buy electricity from Tibber too.

4.2 Important findings from academia

Tibber is an excellent example of a new IT-driven company that has exploited favorable regulatory and market conditions in Norway to the fullest. This can enable them to expand into other market segments if they choose to. Effect based tariffs is one of the regulatory issues that can boost this expansion.

We also observe the need for the local ecosystem manager to create (and own) unique assets. In Tibber's case, examples are their own HAN-port reader, their own electricity usage pattern recognizer and the spot market trading robot. It could be that some of these tools are not very advanced, but it clearly shows the importance of creating value on your own as a local ecosystem manager. Just collecting and relaying other ecosystem partner's services is a much weaker position to hold. This is also observed by [17] in their definition of a platform-based business model:

"A platform market is a market where user interactions are mediated by an intermediary, the platform provider, and are subject to network effects. As opposed to a marketplace or trading exchange, a platform intermediary must offer inherent value beyond the simple mediation process for the two sides of the market. This added-value usually comes from ICT and the associated complementary innovation that increases utility and attractiveness of the platform to all user groups."

Finally, having a considerable number of global service providers (in this case the EV-market) makes it much easier to expand internationally, especially when the Norwegian EV-market is

the most developed in the world. But there is also risk involved in direct integration with these global actors, as “API-taximeters” can be introduced at a later stage. It also requires a bigger work load on continuously updating of many APIs.

The paper [17] called “Platform markets and energy services – EPRG working paper 1334” published by University of Cambridge – energy policy research group was made available to us after the publication of D9.4, although it was written as far back as December 2013. So, the authors were way ahead of their time, and the paper is highly relevant, confirming many of our theses put forward in D9.4, as well as examples of the new kind of market players like Tibber and GreenEnergy using platform-based business models now. Below we have listed some relevant quotes from this paper supporting this view.

“We revise the dominant definition that includes interaction mediation and network externalities as necessary and sufficient conditions by adding complementary innovation, inherent added-value, and a role for ICT as necessary criteria for the definition of a platform.”

“Achieving platform status in an industry comes through building relationships with external complementor firms and establishing leadership in a broader ecosystem (Gawer & Cusumano (2002)).”

“In the case of energy, there are two options for the price of electricity sold from suppliers to consumers; the platform provider could fully internalize the costs for transactions into its fees, or the platform could set its fees independently from the suppliers selling price of electricity” (The first part resembles the Tibber case and the latter resembles the Smartly case.).

“Market liberalisation and recent policy-driven changes are transforming the system into a decentralised value constellation. From a vertically bundled supply chain, electricity network industries are morphing into networks with multiple entry and exit points and new business models, as did the telecom industry following liberalisation (Li & Whally 2002).”

“The value of domestic consumers as grid resources is at the heart of the transition to a platform market for electricity. The complexity of the consumer side, as uptake devices, generators, and flexible resources, with differentiated elasticities of demand, is what makes a platform mediator coming with smart optimisation capabilities viable and even necessary.”

(The introduction of energy related IoT units especially at the consumer/prosumer side is at the core of the INVADE project.)

“Beyond the role of the traditional aggregator, which is to bundle multiple EV reserves in the wholesale or balancing markets, a platform market here suggests the existence of diverse added -value services through complementary innovation and ICT.” (Exemplified through Greenflux’ smart charging offerings to the end-customers and Smartly’s bundling of EV aggregation with other energy services).

“The platform provider effectively shields consumers from variable time-of-use prices that are both inconvenient for them to track and understand, and that expose them to price risks that are beyond their control. In exchange for this “protection”, consumers offer the platform the right to control – fully or partially – their load according to the optimal production times in the system.” (this is very much at the heart of the INVADE project’s main idea, and also confirms our conclusion in D9.2 regarding user behaviour and preferences.)

“We also conclude that while the platform service could be provided by incumbent utilities and ESCOs, the value of the service justifies the entry of third-party entrants distinct from existing players. These new entrants will have the additional benefits of stimulating innovation and new capital investment in the sector. ICT companies can bring new capabilities for smart energy management as well as for fostering complementary innovation in the market.” (Esmart and Greenflux are just two examples of new entrants coming from outside the existing energy utilities, whereas Smartly is an example of such an entrant coming from within).

“Reviewing the literature on platform markets, we emphasise the “intelligence” aspect of a platform, as well as the opportunity to innovation and the establishment of innovation ecosystems, which distinguish it from ordinary marketplaces or input-supplier relationships in traditional markets”. (This confirms the importance of the establishment of ecosystems for both service diversification as well as innovation strength, especially regarding combinatorial innovation).

5 Method

How are we testing and validating the questions mentioned in section 3?

1. Interviews with relevant stakeholders from the Exploitation User Group (EUG) and others beyond the project.
 - How does the business model framework (D9.4) fit with their reality?
 - Which improvements to the framework are needed to fit with their reality, or should the companies themselves consider changing role or BM?
 - Which stakeholders are likely candidates for roles in the business model framework?
2. Implementation of the BM framework in the pilots.
 - How does the business model framework (D9.4) fit with the pilots’ reality?

- Which modifications to the framework are needed to fit with the pilot realities or vice versa?
- 3. Implementation of the BM framework in external exploitation cases
 - How does the business model framework (D9.4) fit with the cases' reality?
 - Which modifications to the framework has been needed to fit into exploitation cases from outside the project?
- 4. Do we find examples in the energy market outside the Invade project?

The process will be oriented to the Osterwalder method. Every business model that is deemed promising will be described in a completed business model canvas. Moreover, the business models will be categorised. The essential parameters for this process, (e.g. ownership and operating models), will be defined, thus creating an INVADE-specific framework of business modelling.

Figure 4 Relationships between the different INVADE WPs

Figure 5: Drawing of interaction and flow

6 Results

6.1 Feedback from EUG workshops

The concepts from the business models were presented in the context of the EUG workshop in Copenhagen on 6 March 2019. This workshop took the form of presentations and panel discussions, with questions and pointers from the audience, primarily consisting of EUG members. The topics presented creating business models for flexibility operators on a high level, followed by a summary of how this was translated into the project pilots. Each of the pilot owners presented the business models as they were to be looked at in the project (except for the Bulgarian pilot who was unable to travel at that time). Due to delays in piloting, the business model aspects of the pilots were also very conceptual, as there were no results to show from the piloting phase. Finally, there were presentations from externally oriented exploitation cases related to the INVADE projects, and the discussion was opened to the audience to see what potential synergies could be pursued for further exploitation.

This section summarises the feedback gathered on the business model framework aspects, including key discussion points from the sessions. Further discussion on the exploitation cases and opportunities identified beyond the project is detailed in deliverable D3.6. Feedback was collected in the form of a Kahoot survey, and included 22 respondents from various backgrounds (utilities, ESCOs, governmental, etc).

6.1.1 Platform-based business models in energy

A large part of the workshop dealt with the value of the IIP developed in the project. The idea of a global flexibility provider that can serve a global ecosystem, where platforms can specialise in different customer segments, and can interact for a mutual benefit seemed logical. Indeed, most of the audience (18 of 22) was very favourable to the benefits of the PBBM within the context of flexibility.

Figure 6: EUG workshop - general feedback on the platform-based business models for flexibility

The mutual benefit from this network effect was agreed upon by the present stakeholders, but there was some concern on two aspects: the added complexity for each interconnection between third party platforms, as well as whether there is enough value in flexibility trading to support all the different ecosystem players. Both of these concerns couldn't be addressed at the time of the EUG workshop, as results from pilots were needed to verify the performance of the business models in these aspects.

6.1.2 Business models including flexibility as part of a larger service offer

One point that has been put forward in Deliverable D9.4 is that in the case of local ecosystem providers, the role of flexibility operator – one who uses flexibility in assets to trade services to another stakeholder – is rarely taken by an actor whose BM is entirely dealing with flexibility. Flexibility is rather a part of a combination of services that is necessary to make a favourable business case. This was clearly detailed by the Norwegian pilot and was mirrored by a stakeholder of the EUG who is providing energy services to real-estate companies. In their case, they provide a portfolio of services to the real-estate companies who manage large buildings and are looking to use the flexibility in these assets for a second market segment in BRPs. This is in line with the business model described by the Norwegian pilot in section **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** and reflects the status of the industry outside of INVADE.

6.1.3 Main drivers for the business models

Some of the business models coming from the project are also being tested in external exploitation cases described in the following sections on business model validation. Here,

eSmart Systems identified the following drivers as main factors contributing to the business case:

1. Building owners who are interested in using flexibility services because they are installing PV infrastructure to be more “green”. There are no incentives in Norwegian regulations to sell electricity back to the grid, so they want to increase their self-consumption.
2. Large charging stations with many charge points behind one transformer, where using flexibility services to avoid needing to pay for a new transformer.

6.1.4 Business model for using V2G

The business model for using V2G/V2X was not discussed in depth during the March Copenhagen workshop, because neither the Dutch or Norwegian pilots had yet implemented this in practice. This topic was covered on a high level, where stakeholders remain optimistic regarding the business potential of the technology, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 7: EUG workshop - General feedback on the outlook of V2X as a business solution for flexibility

However, initial comments from GreenFlux and Elaad from the work they’ve done on the subject showed the following concerns for the V2G/X business model:

- The business case for V2X depends a lot on the cost of stationary batteries. With this cost falling rapidly, there won’t be an interesting case for V2X.
- The double taxation for feeding electricity as well as consumption in the Netherlands continues to hurt the business case for V2G (Double taxation: you first buy the energy with tax, then deliver it back and then you buy it again with tax).

- Vehicle OEMs haven't truly embraced V2X, and other than in experimental pilot cases, the availability of this technology on a commercial level remains limited.

6.2 Interviews with external stakeholders

The feedback from the EUG workshop detailed in section 6.1 was instrumental to harnessing high level feedback on what was put forward in Deliverable D9.4 and how this was interpreted in each of the pilots. However, more in-depth effort was needed to explore the issues identified in the workshop.

A series of interviews was carried out from May to August 2019 with experts representing different stakeholders, such as utilities, grid operators, municipalities, aggregators, etc. The interview work was conducted by WP3, and much of the content is included in Deliverable 3.6. But aspects pertaining to the PBBM framework and business models adopted by flexibility operators in the project are more relevant for WP9.

6.2.1 Background on interview participants

Interviews subjects were solicited from different stakeholder backgrounds, and with representatives from the different pilot countries. **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**8 shows which type of stakeholder participated in the interviews, while **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**9 provides the geographical representation. Note that the respondent from Germany included here synthesised views from discussions held at a local workshop and provides feedback from the point of view of a grid operator as well as centralized storage owner & operator.

Figure 8: Interview participants by stakeholder type

Figure 9: Interview participants by country

6.2.2 Applicability of the platform-based business model framework in the energy industry

The first question in the interview was directly commenting on the PBBM framework put forward in deliverable D9.4. Here, respondents were asked if they agreed with the disruptive potential of the PBBM model and how it was depicted in the framework.

Figure 10: Stakeholder feedback - Disruptive nature of PBBMs

All respondents agreed on an overall level, as show in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, but some of them raised some issues with the framework as it was presented.

The first topic raised as an issue for the framework, where respondents mentioned that “it’s hard to compare the energy industry with Airbnb or Netflix, because of the highly regulated nature of this critical industry”, and “It is not clear that any player will become dominant enough to encourage regulation to permit the business concepts in the framework”.

The second major concern raised regarded the value of the framework as a tool for stakeholders looking to adopt business models that are similar to those tested in the project. One respondent representing an aggregator that includes flexibility in its portfolio said that the way the INVADE generic framework is laid out, there is no clear use for him. In fact, what this respondent said was there is not enough clarity on the benefits that each player receives within

the framework. Furthermore, the terms describing *ecosystems*, as well as *local* and *global* roles were too abstract and brought no value.

Specific recommendations on how to adapt the INVADE framework to different stakeholders' situations are summarized in *Table 1*.

Table 1: Feedback from stakeholders: necessary adjustments in the INVADE business model framework concepts to be applicable in their business

What could be adjusted in the INVADE business model concepts to make it applicable to your business reality?
“The INVADE business model framework concepts lack definition of ownership of platforms / infrastructure”
“Building ecosystems is far from our reality: first optimize business of our company (utility), and once every company does this, the concepts can then be opened with other actors”
“There should be a connection to trading flexibility on eventual flexibility markets”
“We are currently focused on large consumers, but we will examine flexibility from residential consumers and EVs in an upcoming project (NORFLEX)”

6.2.3 Role of the Flexibility Operator (FO)

Finally, the stakeholder interviews explored the role of the FO as put forward in the project and how this relates to the business models of industry actors.

Figure 11: Feedback from stakeholders - the concept of the FO

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. shows that stakeholders generally understand the role of the FO, and its relevance in the exchange of flexibility between flexibility providers and flexibility users. However, the way this role is translated into industry actors was not clear to all respondents:

- “Will it be a new activity that will be taken on by existing players, or it is going to be performed by new companies, playing a new role in the market?”

- “Who will own the FO platform? The ownership of the INVADE platform lacks definition. This is a concern for platforms that provide service exchange, which should be independent from other market actor interests”

On another note, one respondent stated that the FO business models described in INVADE are not new. He gave the example of Entelios, an energy trader in Norway that has employed such business models since 2014, where they are providing energy services to large consumers, and using their flexibility to sell services to BRPs and TSOs.

Figure 12: Feedback from stakeholders - Which players are best suited for FO role.

Feedback was also provided on which type of industry players are best suited to take on the role of FO, as shown in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..** Here the two most suggested business types are aggregators and retailers.

As was the case in the EUG workshop described in section 6.1, stakeholders were interested in seeing how flexibility trading could be stacked among a battery of other energy services. A summary of the services mentioned is shown in *Table 2*.

Table 2: Feedback from stakeholder interviews: Additional services for FO business models

What kind of additional services could a (G)FO provide?
Forecasting
Optimization (assets)
Access to markets
Contracts management
A local market to reflect the energy in the grid (local for local)
Bundling flexibility with in surrounding industries & markets (ex: fixed income from hotel, hospital, V2G business models).

Access to INVADE platform data also makes it possible to increase the number of services to customers (ex: sustainability management). The more services available, the easier it is to attract customers and the longer they tend to stay.

6.3 Interviews with pilot owners and analyses of the emerging pilots and their results

In this subchapter we will validate how the different INVADE-pilots recognize the business model framework and the business/lean canvas developed for their specific pilot in D9.4. Most of the input here is based on the discussions we had with the pilot owners and eSmart in the workshop held in Copenhagen ultimo September 2019.

6.3.1 The Norwegian pilot – Smartly

6.3.1.1 Description

Smartly delivers energy and smart home-based services, mainly focusing on the housing association and business market. In the InvaDE project, the energy services domain has been extended to include flexibility services in these two market segments, including the residential market.

Smartly thus acts as a flexibility operator, delivering flexibility services towards end-customers. They do not take the flexibility role regarding flexibility trading and aggregation in the upstream market, but this remains a future option that depends heavily on the regulation of the DSOs.

6.3.1.2 Pilot architecture

The pilot includes the use of a variety of different energy-IoT units at the customer premises, and end-users IoT-portfolio can vary between just having a smart EV-charger to having installations including PV, smart EV charging, floor heating, thermal storage as well as batteries. For a more comprehensive and technical description, see D4.2 and D10.6. Validation of the Platform-Based Business Model framework applied to this pilot.

In the Interview with the Smartly Chief Product Officer (CPO), we have tested our proposed model from D9.4 to validate this. The feedback was that the model gives a correct picture, and that Smartly does deploy a platform-based business model. In fact, this has been the model from the start, but in the beginning only focusing on smart home services. However, the model includes the DSO as an active part, and this is not true. But they have plans on looking into this upstream flexibility market. Smartly also confirms that they have an extensive ecosystem of partners, and Schneider is just one of them with their smart EV charger.

The CPO recognizes several examples of global service providers (ecosystem partners), and many of them are aggregation partners, meaning that they take care of some of the complexity for Smartly. Overkiz does this for the Smart Home services, Wago does this for the business segment and Cloudcharge does this for the EV services.

Today Smartly has several levels of price sensitivity in their services. And all the customer loads are prepared to be controlled for flexibility services and upstream trading. This is necessary to take on the role as local flexibility operator.

Smartly improves the customer contract duration period for sister companies like Altibox and Lyse Energisalg (energy retailer). This is also a competitive edge enabling control of the data infrastructure. To achieve this anti-churn effect, Smartly takes responsibility for financing the high investment costs for the customer, which allows for the installation (and control) of more flexibility resources.

This is very different from the Badenova case where they only control the energy infrastructure.

The Lean canvas from D9.4 is wrong with respect to leasing. Smartly rents out the equipment to the customers.

Regarding the Lean Canvas, there are more revenue streams possible now. Examples are charging, energy trading cost reduction and backup-services. This is overlapping with the results from Germany and Spain.

Figure 13: Smartly's business model in the INVADE pilot

From D9.4 we see that Smartly in the pilot period deployed a platform-based business model, and they have taken the role as the local ecosystem manager, which also includes the flexibility operator role. But as a local ecosystem manager they do more than just providing flexibility services. They did not start with providing flexibility services, they started to deliver other services, which also means that they can control the different IoT-devices in the home, housing association or company. A very important finding is that the service and market starts with the sourcing, in this case the customers comes first (downstream), then the upstream market (trading and aggregation) comes next.

6.3.1.3 Business models input for relevant stakeholders

The residential market has low margins, so a flexibility optimizing in this market from eSmart needs to be low priced. The commercial buildings are more relevant for the flexibility market. eSmart can like Overkiz in the Smart Home (SH) market take the aggregation role towards the DSOs and BRPs in the Norwegian market. This is a service that Smartly explicitly say they need. This indicates that a flexibility operator role can be divided between a local and global flexibility role, where the local flexibility operator takes care of the control of energy IoT-units, deliver other services and handle the customer relationship. On the other hand, the global flexibility operator can take care of the more complex aggregation, data storage, flexibility exchange and trading part.

This will require that the service is cheaper than with Smartly doing this on their own. If not, this will be developed by Smartly themselves, starting with the DSOs where they are located.

eSmart believes that the best market for eSmart is in the upstream market, and the platform is best suited for aggregation and trading. But so far, they see their role as being a provider of FO software, not to act as a flexibility role neither upstream nor downstream. But the discussion of this role is still ongoing in eSmart.

This mean that there is a customer demand for a global flexibility operator that can do the flexibility trading/market place position, and the IIP and eSmart can fill this position.

Lean Canvas		Flexibility services Local ecosystem – Norwegian pilot		12. October 2018 Iteration 1	
Ecosystem partners Schneider Esmart Eaton Fronius	Problem 1. Customers do not understand the energy markets, especially the concept of flexibility. 2. Customers do not want more work in their everyday life. 3. Customers want to save money on their energy bill. 4. Prosumers cannot exploit their own solar production optimally. 5. Multi-tenant customers and EV-cost	Solution 1. SW and algorithms handles work and complexity 2. No worries 3. Combination of EV billing, enduser flexibility solution and HA. Key Metrics Total revenue No of customers ARPU Cost saved for the customer	Unique Value Proposition 1. "We will take care of the work, financing and complexity for you" 2. You enjoy your own renewable energy 3. You will save money in the long run (both energy and grid fees)	Unfair Advantage Fair EV-billing Energy measurement in multi-tenant buildings. Supporting different energy IoT suppliers Access to huge customer base, Strong ecosystem partner on AI (global service provider) Channels Internet service distribution	Customer Segments Target customers 1. Complex Multi-tenant buildings (EV, PV, storage, HA). 2. Complex Business customers (EV, PV, storage, HA?) 3. Residential customers, preferably prosumers 4. Consumers (VVB, HA)
	Cost Structure Customer Acquisition costs Investment in equipment Installation and operation Personnel (wages)			Revenue Streams Long term low revenue streams from leasing-service Long term low revenue streams from operation-service	

Note: The Norwegian pilot only contains end-user flexibility services, and does not involve flexibility trading (involving DSO, BRP) due to regulation barriers

Figure 14: Lean Canvas in Norwegian pilot

6.3.1.4 Potential for scalability

Does this case scale? Smartly believes that there is a great potential for upscaling the solution. This is a two-fold upscaling, covering both easy upscaling of their own market uptake, but also to use their own solution in other countries.

Today, the integrated Invade platform provides Smartly with optimized time series for controlling the flexibility sources based on machine learning. If this solution is to be used by

Smartly, it needs to be competitive on price. This is still unclear, as prices have yet to be revealed.

It seems likely that the strength of the IIP- is more related to the more global function of flexibility trading, than optimizing of time series which it is being used today, in particular in the residential market.

6.3.1.5 Contract structure for flexibility

As mentioned above, for the customer the core value (output) can be lower peak tariffs or lower energy cost (per hour), the potential income for the aggregated flexibility is not yet effective or present for the end customer. Contractually, as an operator, Smartly can manage the customers' devices according to a set of rules (rule based or AI), and the customer may or may not be directly compensated for this (indirectly they are compensated by charging their EV at lower rates, or reducing the peak hours to reduce peak tariffs). In the pilot, the flexibility contract is embedded into the standard contract from Smartly with a separate chapter. At the other end, there will be a need for flexibility contracts with counterparts – purchasers of flexibility – such as DSO's, the TSO or others when Smartly chooses to go there, and when regulation of DSOs permit them to trade flexibility.

6.3.2 The Bulgarian pilot – Albena

6.3.2.1 Description

The Bulgarian pilot is located at Albena, where more than 40 hotels are co-located in this area. Albena has had a strong focus on sustainable tourism, where you find elements like up-cycling of food waste, forest preservation, solar power and more. The INVADE project introduces the concept of flexibility services, controlling anything from solar power and batteries to huge water boilers. The purpose is to reduce energy cost, grid peak fees and increase the value of renewable energy production.

6.3.2.2 Pilot architecture

Figure 15: The architecture in the Bulgarian pilot (from D10.1)

6.3.2.3 Validation of The Platform-Based Business Model framework applied to this pilot

The generic Invade platform/ecosystem applied to Albena (NOW)

Figure 16: Albena mapped in the INVADE BM framework (D9.4)

This sub-chapter is based on the workshop held in Copenhagen in September 2019. According to Albena, the use of IIR is not profitable as of today. They can see some improvements, but Albena is not certain how much of this is related to the platform.

Albena will not pursue a FO role themselves, and for now, there is no one who can take this role. For this reason, the flexibility services have had an end-user approach.

Albenas opinion of the mapping in the framework is that it seems ok, and they will also take a closer look at the Lean Canvas exercise, and come back to this if there is need for adjustments.

Albena has experienced a massive setback due to the Thomas Cook bankruptcy during the fall of 2019. So, focusing a lot on the bigger picture (Greta Thunberg-effect, green inclusive etc.) is not getting much attention at this point of time. First, they must sell the IRR story to the top management, which is not easy.

They are willing to extend the trial period, but in the winter time, all the hotels are closed. So, if eSmart is willing to do this, it is an option from Albena.

Looking solely at the hotel industry should be considered as an interesting business case, and this type of business approach could lead to piggy backing on sales which again can boost the scale and sale of the IIP.

Lean Canvas		Flexibility services (only) Local ecosystem – Bulgarian pilot		30. October 2018 Iteration 1	
Ecosystem partners Schneider Esmart SMA (battery)	Problem 1. DSO give high penalties for exceeding power/energy limits. 2. Imported energy is not renewable, and increases the Albena CO2 footprint.. 3. PV produced energy is not used optimally.. 4. High daily peak-hours must be reduced.. 5. How can a green hotel become a competitive advantage	Solution 1. SW and algorithms handles work and complexity 2. API-integration is already done and proved. Saves money and time. 3. Ecosystem partners in place. Key Metrics Total revenue growth Reduction of penalties Customer satisfaction Greener hotel brand ARPU Environmental "savings" per guest	Unique Value Proposition 1. "We both reduce your energy cost, CO2-footprint and power penalties" 2. We enable you to harvest revenues from your installed flexibility resources. 3. We also make your brand greener, by increasing your renewable share. 4. We improve the utilization of your PV-installation (daily, season-wise) All combined !!	Unfair Advantage Strong hotel competence Building your own proof case. Strong environmental competence & practice Strong IoT/Scada partner Access to huge customer base. Strong ecosystem partner on AI (global service provider) Potential ecosystempart. Channels Internet service distribution	Customer Segments Target customers 1. Hotels (prosumer with thermal storage, battery storage, PV, EV) 2. Hotel (consumer with thermal storage) 3. Hotel guests, especially those with a green mindset)
	Cost Structure Investment in equipment (IoT adaptors, PV, EV, batteries, flexible water boilers) Installation and operation			Revenue Streams Reducing peak-penalties Reducing total energy bill (long term investment) Increasing renewables/reducing the CO2 footprint Revenue from flexibility sale	

Note: The customer here is another hotel (chain) and not the hotel guest. Albena replicates their solution is the «living proof» themselves. The combination of high hotel competence, very advanced technologies (like AI) and ecosystem partners and access makes this very hard to copy.

Figure 17: The lean canvas business model for Albena (from D9.4)

6.3.2.4 Business models for relevant stakeholders

As there is no DSO willing to purchase flexibility, and no one that can take the FO-role in Bulgaria, the two other business stakeholders are Schneider and eSmart.

6.3.2.5 Potential for scalability

The potential for up-scaling in the Bulgarian pilot is three-fold:

- The potential for up-scaling at the other 35+ hotels at Albena. They use the same SCADA system as well as the IoT adaptors from Schneider to replicate the solution at Hotel Flamingo Grand and Paradise Blue hotel.
- If eSmart wants to sell the Invade flexibility services to the accommodation and hotel industry, they could do so. However, they should continue to make Hotel Flamingo Grand and Paradise Blue hotel a living proof of cost reduction to succeed.
- If Albena chooses to extend their sustainable and eco-friendly hotel concept, they could make this a separate spin-out business where they demonstrate “walk the

talk”for potential customers. This way, eSmart could piggyback on these sales being an ecosystem partner for the “Albena green concept”.

6.3.2.6 Contract structure for flexibility

So far, no contracts have been made since Albena themselves are consuming the flexibility services inhouse.

6.3.3 The Dutch pilot – GreenFlux

6.3.3.1 Description

The Dutch pilot corresponds to use case 1 focusing on EV battery as the source for flexibility. This pilot involves 4 sub cases based upon source of flexibility: 1) charging points at large scale offices, 2) charging points in large scale public places, 3) charging points at several homes and private users, and 4) small scale public offices. Flexibility services to be tested are: congestion management, voltage/reactive power control, ToU optimization, KWmax control and self-balancing. Beneficiaries of the services are DSO, and prosumers.

6.3.3.2 Pilot architecture

The concept architecture provides information flow in the Dutch pilot. As mentioned before there are four sub-pilots - 2 of each managed by GreenFlux (GF) and ElaadNL For technical details on communication between systems readers, we refer to D4.2.

Figure 18: GreenFlux pilot structure

Figure 19: eLadNL pilot structure

6.3.3.3 Validation of The Platform-Based Business Model framework applied to this pilot

The company today offers remote service management for charging spots, metering and billing services to owners of local charging spots. It gathers information on charging times of its customers and of customer’s customer. It already has infrastructure in place and together with energy use information it can ‘crowdsource’ flexibility from its existing large customer base. The framework presented in D9.4 fits very well to this case.

Figure 20: Basic GreenFlux with grid directed services

The pilots prove that crowdsourcing of flexibility can technically work to meet the needs of various stakeholders. However, the implementation of flexibility procurement and delivery have been different from the proposed framework. In absence of FO as a separate market player, eSmart provided the intelligence behind flexibility management. Many positives have emerged from all the 4 sub-pilots. Elaad’s sub-pilots showed that hosting capacity of the existing grid can be increased. Also, the need to invest heavily on grid reinforcement by DSOs can be delayed by smart charging. Flexibility value for DSO has become clear from the project while value for prosumers depends on a variety of factors. Some key learnings regarding flexibility value to prosumers are:

- Potential value emerges when multi EV loads are stacked together, i.e. consolidation of flexibility assets.
- Households are more interested in buying green energy.

- EV smart charging to maximize self-consumption in households does not yield any benefit because at the time of generation vehicles are at work place. Without storage, which again is expensive, flexibility value is limited to such customers. As such, value propositions for household customers' needs more investigation.
- Electricity price fluctuations in the market are too low to provide savings for customers. As such, limit of kWmax takes the precedence for optimization.
- In the Netherlands there is no seller in the market which is selling electricity based upon changes in the spot market. To monetarily benefit, non-commercial players like EV owners and households' appropriate tariff-schemes are required.
- Without contractual binding of FO to provide benefits (like savings in electricity bill, lower charging cost or additional revenues) there wouldn't be interest among customers to participate in the flexibility market. Additionally, this would also create trust among market players. For player like GreenFlux currently there is no way to assess if flexibility management algorithm will deliver the proposed benefit. A flexibility management system being proprietary software of eSmart is a black box to outside players who do not know how effective the algorithms are. Thus, it has become clear that for a FO to sell its services, there needs to be some guarantee in contracts. For players like GreenFlux it is natural to take role of FO as the market develops further - thereby gaining market of flexibility.

GreenFlux understands the value of being a FO in the market. However, according to their analysis the market is not yet ready for such business. Their core business is providing charging solutions (both hardware and software) and smart charging is an energy business on itself. Their goal for the moment is to focus on their strength and capture the market for EV charging. Once that is achieved and market for flexibility is ripe, they would eventually move towards broader flexibility management.

Elaad does not have a business model of their own but, being funded by the Dutch DSO's, understands the business of DSOs and can relate to it. One of the take-aways from the project is that a grid operator can successfully set limits on functioning of a FO and that by doing so, a DSO can prevent overloads on grid capacity, regardless of the strategy followed by the FO.

Figure 21: The GreenFlux business model in Invade as described in D9.4

6.3.3.4 Business models for relevant stakeholders

Based upon the Dutch pilot, 3 key stakeholders are identified whose business model would be affected with the INVADE platform. These are CPO (GreenFlux), DSO, and charging station owners. Lean canvasses are developed to show how their existing business model will be affected. The description in gray color for each block in the canvas shows original business and description in black provides new characteristics emerging with INVADE platform.

<p>Problems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Managing group of charging in user friendly and cost-effective way Managing and executing invoices and payment efficiently Support EV roaming for 	<p>Solution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete solution to manage large charging infrastructure including billing Remote support Financial and transaction processing services 	<p>Unique value proposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> GF offers unique cloud-based service and operation platform GF’s novel flexibility platform provides easy solutions 	<p>Unfair advantage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embedded high-tech controller Contracts with manufacturers of chargers Strong association with ElaadNL 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private parking space owners Public parking space owners EV owners Prosumers DSOs/utilities
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<p>convenient billing and payment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consolidating flexibility for economical gain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploitation of locally produced electricity • INVADE platform 	<p>based open protocols and systems, allowing every charging station to connect to the platform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregate highly available flexibility for load and cost reduction under one platform 		
	<p>Key Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of GF activated charging spots • Geographic spread • Number of flexibility customer • Number of flexibility providers 		<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet • Existing app • Manufacturer of chargers • ElaadNL • Direct dialogue with DSO 	
<p>Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personals • R&D • IT costs (including Licenses costs) • Risk management 		<p>Revenue streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service management fees • Billing services fees • Flexibility services fees 		

Figure 22: Lean canvas for GreenFlux business model with flexibility. Adapted from D9.4.

6.3.3.5 Potential for scalability

GreenFlux (GF) claims to have access to 52.000 EV charging stations in 10 countries in Europe via the Open Charge Point Interface (OCPI) roaming protocol connected to many service providers in Europe. This implies that the case can be scaled to these many assets amounting to managing 220.000 payment transactions per month. GF with its own platform and support from INVADE can scale the flexibility functionality to all its users.

DSOs are able to manage a huge number of EVs if they can manage the grid in a smart way. Does the INVADE platform give an opportunity to support this?

There is a new kind of contract entering the Dutch market. This contract type is not only based on a fixed kWmax fee (based on the fuse size). In the new contract the DSO can also add new requirements like reducing loads in the household.

Elaad does not foresee any flexibility operator acting in the DSO market (distribution network) in the next 5 years.

Elaad is entering into a new project, utilizing other mechanisms than use of an FO to handle load shifting responsiveness, using effect based tariffs.

According to Elaad, the new energy package from EU, “Clean energy for all Europeans”, is supporting the change towards a smarter energy market, but that EU is missing some points related to Smart Charging.

Today technical support for smart charging is too fluffy, and there is a need for more detailed standardization.

Elaad is capable of testing all new chargers and cars, and does this for the Netherlands.

But they are somewhat reluctant as of today to step up and take a European position.

6.3.3.6 Contract structure for flexibility

The Flexibility Operator role with relevant contracts have not been specified in depth by GreenFlux.

6.3.4 The German pilot – Badenova

6.3.4.1 Description

In the German pilot, Badenova is leveraging flexibility from a combination of centralized and decentralised battery systems to relieve grid issues. Here, the Badenova Group’s

DSO (bnNETZE) is experiencing over-voltages due to a high share of renewable energy generation. In addition high fees due to power peaks in the entire electrical grid of bnNETZE shall be avoided. Otherwise they must be paid to the upstream grid operator. One issue that the pilot addresses in business model development is the lack of revenues or incentives for private households offering flexible capacity of their energy storage assets.

The services Badenova are testing in the pilot are as follows:

- Installing a centralized energy storage (CES) to improve local voltage stability.
- Using CES and distributed energy storage (DES) for peak shaving to reduce peak fees for DSO.
- Remunerating private households for participating in a peak shaving business model by lowering their electricity bills through reduced network usage fees.

6.3.4.2 Pilot architecture

The pilot explores the use of CES to improve autonomously local voltage stability in a weak part of the grid. In addition, CES is used for peak shaving. Therefore, the CES device - a redox flow battery - communicates to the INVADE platform through a battery management system BMS.

There is also the use of decentralized energy storage (DES) assets installed at customer homes which are controlled by SMA home management systems. These communicate data to the INVADE platform which returns optimised operation schedules. The detailed pilot architecture is described in INVADE deliverable D4.2.

6.3.4.3 Validation of Platform-Based Business Model framework applied to this pilot

Deliverable D9.4 suggests a business model framework for Badenova, where a subsidiary of Badenova can seize the position of local FO and provide services to prosumers, DSOs and BRPs within their regional focus area in Freiburg. Furthermore, the integration with the SMA gateways creates the opportunity for a global FO to cater to a global ecosystem built on the SMA backbone.

Extensive work was performed in WP10 to adapt the concepts in D9.4 and explore business models in the context of the German pilot. Among the validation steps conducted as described in Deliverable D10.5, Badenova had the tasks of:

- Developing new contract types for interconnecting customer DES assets;

- Compare different solutions, including implementing CES, to solve DSO challenges for avoiding over voltages in the weak grid area;
- Evaluating the cost savings of addressing peak power fees with the flexibility platform that leverages DES;
- Evaluating additional revenues for customers when using flexibility management for more than local optimization of self-consumption.

The implementation of platform-based business model framework from deliverable D9.4 into in the German pilot was performed as shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Validation of the business model framework in the German pilot.

The local FO role embraced by Badenova caters to the local ecosystem that was described in deliverable D9.4. In adopting the framework to the German pilot in the INVADE context, where the business for operating BESS to provide flexibility to the grid is studied, it is important to identify where lies the ownership and operation of the batteries. This is particularly relevant for the German pilot in the case of DES, where the control and ownership of the storage does not lie with the same actors within the Badenova group, as shown in Figure 23.

The larger ecosystem described in D9.4 where a global FO can build on the backbone established by SMA inverters and provide services to players on a larger scale, outside Badenova's focus area isn't demonstrated in the pilot. However, there is an opportunity

for the INVADE platform to aggregate many assets in order to access new market segments including the ancillary market. This is expanded in the following sub-section.

6.3.4.4 Business models for relevant stakeholders

The business model for Badenova described in D9.4 was tested, and work package 10 tested the financial value of using DES and CES for grid support as mentioned in D10.5. The results of these tests are included in deliverable D10.6, and general findings include:

- As assessed in the pilot, grid reinforcement (€ 123,000) would have been slightly cheaper than using CES (€ 129,000) for delaying grid upgrades.
- When operating 10 DES located in the private households to support the DSO, the savings potential depending on what voltage level the storage is located ranges between 90 and 115 € / kWa. This was tested using 10 DES devices, but assessed with scenarios using 1000 interconnected DES with varying capacities. The savings potentials are described in detail in deliverable D10.6 and start to be significant with more available households. However, this assessment is not considering the reimbursement which much be payed to households making their flexibility available to the FO. Furthermore, the INVADE platform allows the FO to integrate many devices which cater to the FO's business model, especially considering the future market penetration of storages. Yet, each integration nonetheless brings an inherent added complexity to the system and a cost to the FO, which currently is more interested in integrating larger systems which can provide the same available capacity with a single interconnection instead of 1000, for example.

As a result of the work implementing the business models in the German pilot, the business models most interesting for FOs in Germany rely on stacking multiple services with the same storage device. This business model, which is heavily modified from that proposed in deliverable D9.4 is illustrated in Figure 24.

<p>Problem</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Largest 15 min peak leads to high yearly peak fees for large prosumers. • Large prosumers with PV, EV chargers, critical loads are investing in BESS for and peak shaving, but this is not enough to make purchasing BESS an interesting business case 	<p>Solution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predict the peaks to do peak shaving with to lower peak fees. • Manage the use of the battery between the peaks to provide stacked services • Aggregate flexibility to provide services to DSOs and BRPs 	<p>Unique Value Proposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of the peak prices which is the immediate concern of customers and grid operators (both affected) • Maximizing added value of the BESS flexibility between peaks to make the business of battery interesting. • Aggregating assets and using single API of INVADE platform to access other markets (ex: qualifying for BRP) 	<p>Unfair Advantage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Close relationship with DSO (part of same group) • Exclusive agreement with HAS/EMS supplier (SMA) 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large prosumers with different generation, loads and storage assets. • DSO • BRP
<p>Key Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of peak tariffs • Increase in self-consumption • Aggregated 	<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct sales as services to customer of retailer 			
<p>Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of making assets controllable • Compensation to customers who make assets available • INVADE platform costs 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subscription or performance-based contract with prosumers for services (peak-shaving, emergency, self consumption) • Services on ancillary markets, DSO support • Power exchange 		

Figure 24: Lean canvas for the Badenova FO business model

6.3.4.5 Potential for scalability

Data processing is easily handlebar and widely scalable as SMA is providing the data infrastructure for the distributed energy storages. Since SMA is the market leader for solar hardware in Germany, Badenova seeks a strong cooperation with this company. The SMA system already provides a widely used home management system called “Sunny Home Manager”, which is capable of forecasting PV-generation and load consumption and to calculate on this basis an operation scheme for the local battery. This system is furthermore capable of connecting devices of different manufacturers. This is an important advantage as INVADE does not have to deal with a variety of proprietary communication standards of devices on the lower house level. Instead INVADE can focus solely on connecting to the SMA-cloud platform for collecting data as all Sunny Home Manager devices send relevant data to this platform. So it acts like a middle ware.

An interface between the SMA cloud platform and INVADE has been programmed by Badenova. It can deal with numerous households without restrictions. So – using this given interface – data processing is easy. On the way back to execute schedules calculated by INVADE specially developed gateways in the households are addressed via a common FTP-Server. Even here data processing is easy to handle. So adapting

new customers to the systems is done very quickly. The most time-consuming step in the process is signing the contracts.

6.3.4.6 Contract structure for flexibility

The German pilot describes a contractual relationship between the DSO and the households who provide flexible battery capacity for peak shaving. This contract dictates the financial compensation that the DSO will provide the households and covers:

- The difference between the cost of self-produced electricity than that purchased from the grid,
- Available power for flexibility
- Frequency and number of flexibility activations.

6.3.5 The Spanish pilot – EPESA

6.3.5.1 Description

Aligned with the overall objective of the project, the Spanish Pilot addresses use case 2, where a centralized energy storage system is installed at a secondary substation with the objective of providing flexibility to the DSO and BRP through the INVADE platform. The objectives of the INVADE project are addressed in the Spanish pilot by testing and validating the use of flexibility by the Spanish DSO (Estabanell); expecting that the findings provided by this use case will allow a better usage of the grid and therefore potentiate the increase of the share of renewables in the electric grid. At Estabanell, a 210kWh battery was installed at a secondary substation inside the company's headquarters. This battery is connected to a power electronics device which controls the battery and allows the DSO to manage the grid at the pilot location.

6.3.5.2 The Platform-Based Business Model framework applied to this pilot

The framework of a platform-based business model applies to this case in the sense where it is possible to verify the implementation of the platform (IIP) to be used by a newly created role (FO) and sell/provide services to several users.

In the Spanish pilot, the concept of FO is tested. The FO operates a set of flexibility assets (in the Spanish pilot it is a battery) due to the INVADE platform. The technical feasibilities of this concept were validated with the Catalan pilot; whereas the detailed economic viability is still to be validated. It was identified during the pilot that pricing

flexibility is of importance when assessing the right business model to be implemented for each role.

In general, a platform-based business model can be applied in this set-up, however further developments need to be done, to validate the contracts, the way of monetizing the flexibility and the right business model to be applied.

6.3.5.3 Pilot's asset and communication

In the Spanish pilot, the two assets are in place: 1 battery, 1 PED (power electronics device). The main communication in the systems are 1) communication between INVADE platform and DSO systems, 2) communication between INVADE platform and BRP systems, and 3) communication between INVADE platform and battery. The pilot architecture clearly shows the information exchange between assets (see Figure 25).

All other “services” have bidirectional communications, as the arrows indicate in Figure 25. The critical infrastructure belongs to the DSO. It was defined in previous deliverables that the FO role would be taken by the BRP. If the regulatory boundaries were not a barrier, the Spanish pilot could have a potential to apply a real platform business model by creating a triangular communication between DSO, BRP and flexibility operator ‘Mercator’ (Eisenmann, Parker & Alstyne 2006). The pilot also fulfils complementing the platform business model definitions by Hagiu & Wright (2011) that the FO can serve as a mediator which enables BRP and DSO interact with each other.

Figure 25: Spanish pilot assets and communication.

6.3.5.4 Business models for relevant stakeholders

The existing stakeholders applied to the Spanish pilot are represented in the previous figure (above): BRP, DSO, FO and battery owner. Considering these relevant stakeholders, lean canvas is developed to describe each business services and attributes of the model.

Lean Canvas		SPANISH PILOT			12. November 2019
Ecosystem partners Esmart Schneider CPO	Problem 1. DSO faces reactive power problems during high PV electricity influx. 2. Congestion in distribution network at peak hours. 3. DSO wants to delay grid investments. 4. BRP wants to reduce imbalances. 5. BRP wants to improve their day ahead and intraday portfolio using storage.	Solution 1. Centrally located storage in distribution grid provides multiple services to both DSO and BRP. 2. Load management at building. Key Metrics 1. Energy & power reduction 2. Islanding Time 3. BRP cost savings 4. Capacity of the Grid 5. Grid invest. Reduction 6. Optimize Diesel Generation	Unique Value Proposition 1. Better renewable integration without additional investment in grid. 2. Better power quality. 3. Security of supply when fault occurs. 4. Increased revenue generation for BRP using storage. 5. Facilitate service exchange and make the local DSO offer unique proposition	Unfair Advantage Unique combination of AI, ML, and DL competence and energy market competence. Channels Internet service distribution	Customer Segments Target customers 1. DSO. 2. BRP 3. Local ecosystem in different market segments. 4. Critical infrastructure.
	Cost Structure Customer Acquisition costs Data platform cost (installation and operation, People, etc. Infrastructure replacement (Battery and PED cost)			Revenue Streams Long term low revenue streams from BRP portfolio optimize. Long term low revenue streams from BRP's self balancing. Long term low revenue streams from DSO for avoiding congestion, providing peak power. Grid investment and CO ₂ reduction,	

Figure 26: Lean canvas applied to Spanish pilot

6.3.5.5 Potential for scalability

The implementation of the INVADE platform can be considered as a first step in the scalability. In the Spanish market and electricity sector there are no conditions in which the pilot users would have real benefit from this solution at the current date, but it is predicted that in the near future this kind of solutions will be imperative, as the electricity system evolves.

6.3.5.6 Contract structure for flexibility

The contract structure is commented and described in D10.3. This includes the terms under which the contracts between the different stakeholders could be set up. As noted there, it is important to note that the FO is a figure which is not legal in Spain.

Regarding contract structure, in D10.3 it was proposed that contracts should define certain parameters which condition the way flexibility is traded.

Although these contractual efforts for flexibility was not implemented, it could be recommended for future flexibility operators on the INVADE platform. Contracts of INVADE could be handled under the four following conditions:

1. A compensation for entering/being a part of the contract, e.g. a monthly fee at €/month
2. A compensation related to reservation of flexibility capacity, e.g. a given price at €/kWh
3. A compensation related to activation of flexibility, e.g. a given price at €/kWh
4. A penalty for not delivering the agreed activated flexibility, e.g. a given price at €/kWh

6.3.6 Validation of eSmart business model

6.3.6.1 Description

eSmart Systems is the principal software developer in INVADE. The primary result of the project is supposed to become the new release of their existing Connected Prosumer platform that has been offered on the market for some years. Already some take-aways from the project has been incorporated in intermediate releases. Currently the Connected Prosumer software is sold as a solution package with engineering hours. The segments that have been targeted so far have been Nordic DSOs and commercial property owners which have upgraded facilities such as warehouses with PV panels and other types of non-controllable local production. Maximizing the self-consumption rate to cut costs and exploit the potential that DER offers is the typical rationale for exploring the potential that software-based flexibility support can offer. INVADE must be seen as an extensive upgrade of the existing system.

eSmart Systems's mission statement is formulated as follows: "*Leverage digital intelligence into operational excellence*". It suggests an emphasis on computational power and effective data and information management to support decision making and executional efficiency. However, they have no declared ambition to take on the FO role. They wish to sell energy and flexibility- oriented software as a service with the support of the Azure platform from Microsoft. Currently they apply a direct sales strategy where

bilateral agreements make room for customization and engineering. Their marketing strategy as a pioneer in a market that they consider still immature is to educate and be educated together with other front-runners in the various segments that they address. Their primary objective in the future is to seize the future market with shrink wrapped services that can be activated by “means of a click”. Consequently, their existing role within the scope of the generic business model presented here is as a provider of the platform required to establish the ecosystem.

6.3.6.2 Case architecture

eSmart Systems’s current business model is focused on supporting whoever takes the role of the Flexibility Operator (FO) and those stakeholders i.e. prosumers, battery owners that choose to sign up with the FO. As a platform provider eSmart Systems is not part of the FO ecosystem. Nor does the company aspire to be a value generating party within the ecosystem. However, by providing the underlying software service their business model supports and amplifies the value generation of those stakeholders that are part of the ecosystem (Figure 27).

Figure 27: eSmart Systems aims to support a chain of value generating steps.

As shown in Figure 28 eSmart Systems embraces the platform-based business model framework by providing the technical means needed to make it operational. However, during the project the top management of eSmart Systems has been confronted with the opportunities that the FO role offers and which is reachable for the company if they extend their present business model in that direction. With the cloud-based services they are in a position to adopt the concept of a Global Flexibility Operator with specific

emphasis on computational services, data collection, curation, storage and management (28). This is further illustrated in Figure 29.

Figure 28: eSmart Systems could readily extend their existing model and adopt a central position within the INVADE platform itself.

Figure 29: eSmart Systems has the opportunity to take the active position as nexus in a cloud consisting of multiple INVADE platforms and FOs. cloud.

As such its position would primarily be to host the means to manage big volumes of data and a computational toolbox optimized for use within the energy industry and directly interact with multiple FOs operating local ecosystems, all within the same cloud (see

Figure 30). This ambition is likely to earn the company an important position of the future European Digital Single Market².

Figure 30: eSmart Systems could seize the role of Global Flexibility Operator

In essence the leap from being a passive platform provider to seize the position as the central hub in a comprehensive system of lesser ecosystems is rather small. The technical requirements would be the same. The major difference would be that the new position would enable eSmart Systems to impact the operation from day-to-day and directly control important transactions and revenue streams. The top management of the company has signalled that they will consider this possibility. The introduction of the recently endorsed policy package from the EU Commission, “Clean Energy for All European Citizens”³ suggests that maintaining the current business model could be

² European Commission: “European Cloud Initiative to give Europe a global lead in the data driven economy”. Press release. April 19, 2016, Brussels

³ Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on common rules for the internal market in electricity (recast)

REGULATION (EU) 2019/943 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 5 June 2019 on the internal market for electricity

DIRECTIVE (EU) 2018/2001 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (recast)

strategically useful for eSmart Systems still. This is discussed in detail in deliverable D3.6 on Exploitation and Business Development.

6.3.6.3 Business models for relevant stakeholders

<p>Problem</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How to support a flexibility oriented enterprise in an economical viable way? When to use energy flexibility without jeopardizing basic energy needs, comfort, convenience? How to maximize long-term gains on flexibility? How to manage, interpret and respond to Big Data stemming from many sensors? 	<p>Solution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A cloud-based system to federate flexibility assets and aggregate flexibility An online service that can perform economic optimization of flexibility operations A data hub with a generic API for extensive data harvest and management A platform for building an ecosystem for flexibility 	<p>Unique Value Proposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existing users can reconfigure their connections without having to physically reconnect with new stakeholders Generic and scalable API for connecting to new data sources and feeds. Long standing in energy trade and innovative flexibility operations 	<p>Unfair Advantage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operate within a very liberal energy market Vast experience harvested during extensive R&D and R&I projects 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flexibility Operators Aggregators Commercial property owners Microgrid owners ESCOs (SESP) DSOs BRPs Energy cooperatives and new communities (REC & CEC)
<p>Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs associated with using the Microsoft Azure cloud Cost of commissioning and support 	<p>Key Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scalability (number of users & number of assets) Time and work to connection and commissioning Data volume management Forecast and optimization accuracy and precision Contract design tractability Cost of operation 		<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Through energy related associations Through DER suppliers Through HAS/EMS suppliers Through electro suppliers By means of existing customers/end-users 	
<p>Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs associated with using the Microsoft Azure cloud Cost of commissioning and support 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Membership/commission fee for system/platform participation Strike fee for forecasts and optimization 		

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Figure 31: The Lean Canvas Model description of eSmart Systems current business model.

The LCM that illustrates eSmart Systems' current business model is shown in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..** It can easily be observed that it reflects the characteristics of the INVADE system itself. The LCM further shows that the customer focus is directed towards all those stakeholders that are likely to consider the FO role. To extend the business model, as discussed above and thus take a more active role within the ecosystem that the INVADE system caters for will imply extensions to the LCM described in 31.

Table 3: To adopt the Global Flexibility Operator role eSmart Systems has to make extensions to its present scope of business. The table relates to the existing business model described in Figure 31.

LCM feature	Extension or revision of existing model	Remarks
Problem	<p>How to expand and incorporate multiple FOs and ecosystems?</p> <p>How to ensure standardization of operation and create a viable data space for energy flexibility?</p> <p>How to make the operations of the local FO less costly and more effective?</p>	<p>These extensions pertain to the role of the Central Flexibility Operator role, which emphasizes massive data transactions, storage and an advanced computation toolbox customized for flexibility operation</p>
Solution	<p>Combine the existing provisions for a cloud-based flexibility service (INVADE) with an active insourcing and federation of local FO operations and data streams.</p>	<p>Create economy of scale through a shared economy concept for local FOs.</p>
Key metric	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage space • Cost reductions for FOs and others • Diversity of data and tools available • Member of FOs included • Total member of stakeholders encompassed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wider access and a higher degree of sharing brings cost per participant down and diversity of useful/proven resources up. • Increased number of participants increases the attractiveness of the INVADE to external, stakeholders that see this as a very specialized and homogenous market segment that could lead to new add-on services/products that could benefit all.
Unique value proposition	No significant change	
Unfair advantage	No significant change	

Channels	The cloud itself	A more active promotion could be made possible since it is possible to operate within the ecosystems established.
Customer segments	Those who takes the local FO role and others dependent on these	
Cost structure	Management and marketing functions required increase the costs	Trying to actively recruit and federate lesser and specialized ecosystems will require additional resources that eSmart Systems does not have today.
Revenue streams	Direct control of transactions increases the revenue possibilities	

6.4 Validation of business models in INVADE exploitation cases

6.4.1 The Inspiria Charge Court case

6.4.1.1 Description

Figure 32: Inspiria view

The Inspiria Charge Court (ICC) is one of the exploitation cases in WP3 developed from scratch together with stakeholders that have not been part of the INVADE project. As an exploitation case business models and technical solutions developed in the project were

promoted to test adaptability and viability of the results generated. ICC is a shared economy concept that relates to the idea of a “food court” where different restaurants share the same space and multiple facilities to increase attractiveness and reduce cost. ICC organizes different charging point operators (CPOs) that target different customer segments. Providers of ultra-fast chargers are primarily going to serve bypassers on the E6. Others offer other type of services, i.e. parking spaces equipped with chargers for lease and thus serving a different segment. Loads induced by the simultaneous charging is mitigated by means of a stationary battery, a roof-top PV panel, V2G and smart charging where charging priorities are exchanged in a local market.

6.4.1.2 Case architecture

The plan for ICC is to establish 38 charging points altogether. Currently one 50kW and seven 22kW chargers have been installed. When the roll-out and installations have been completed there will be one 300kW chargers with two outlets. In addition more 22kW and 11kW chargers will be mounted by the CPOs invited in. A 400m² solar panel and a 100-200kWh battery is planned to support load management. The conception to the

Figure 33: Inspiria structure

main supply has a capacity limit of 915 amps. Hence, there is a physical limit for the import and export of electric energy to and from the grid. In addition, max peak management is important to keep costs down, especially during winter time when price per kW for the highest peak reaches €15/kW. To keep costs down, smart charging and other flexibility resources are used to reduce loads. An internal market (see figure 32)

will enable sale of priorities/flexibility to ensure that costs are kept down and that day-to-day operations are kept within the physical limit. As a virtual microgrid ICC will be rigged to serve the local DSO and possibly support the BRP if this one wishes to take part in the balancing market.

6.4.1.3 The Platform-Based Business Model framework applied to this case

The platform-based business model framework presented in D9.4 was used as a recommended blue print for the overall ICC operation. The general idea with a local Flexibility Operator (FO) was adopted. Many of the assets in ICC are owned by Inspiria which operates a science entertainment centre. Neither Inspiria Science centre nor the CPOs invited in wished to become a FO. After several months of searching a candidate for this role was found. A retailer and producer, soliciting new opportunities in the growing EV and renewable market in Norway seized the FO role for this project with the idea of creating a franchise. When Østfold Energi became part of the development project for ICC they further developed the business concept introduced to them. The basic reason was that the conceptual framework presented to them indicated a mechanism for future management of multiple venues like ICC across Norway and when it was time for DSO involvement. However, for a start-up business in a new market, the INVADE concept was too abstract. More substance was needed. Østfold Energi concluded that the FO role had to be taken care of in a new and separate company. The business model for this enterprise is shown below in the Lean Canvas Format. The source behind this was the management and business developers of Østfold Energi. As can be observed from this the original platform-based concept was largely maintained. This is even better illustrated with Østfold Energi's own specification of their venture business found ed on the FO concept. It shows an ecosystem very similar to what INVADE proposed when discussion with Inspiria and Østfold Energi started.

Problem <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity constraints on local infrastructure limit peak demand for charging services Cost of power [NOK/kWh] from the main supply is very high during long periods of the year. Scattered and isolated charging stations are not profitable Grid owner potentially suffers from congestions and voltage problems 	Solution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organize complementary charging and energy services as self-sustainable ecosystem with high attractiveness Manage loads to minimize costs and observe capacity limits Organize court as a flexibility resource for grid owner 	Unique Value Proposition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offer customized charge services for different EV segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bypassers Visitors to the science center Hotel guests Commuters Etc. A shared economy concept for reduced costs and increased demand for charging Cater for inclusion high-margin services into the ecosystem 	Unfair Advantage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Early mover Master of new technologies ENOVA support Smart City development in same area 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CPOs of different kinds Car sharing pool operator (V2G) Parking spot subscribers (e.g. local) Battery owner PV owner
	Key Metrics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Degree of flexibility [kWh/h] Charging time [kWh/min] Demand 1: Visitors per day and per hour Demand 2: Charging volume [kWh] DSO flexibility and dispatch frequency [kWh per day] 		Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web Easy Park app ??? CPO customers Inspiria customers Neighboring offices & hotel Traffic signs 	
Cost structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marketing costs ENOVA contribution Reduced tariff- DSO as non-priority load 			Revenue Streams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Parking pace (w chargers) subscriptions CPO fees BMS and PV commissions 	

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Figure 34: Lean canvas of the planned spinout from Østfold Energi

Ecosystem for a Charge Court

Figure 35: Ecosystem for charge court

6.4.1.4 Business models for relevant stakeholders

The ecosystem depicted in Figure 35 above specifies a number of stakeholders associated with the charge court operation. Most of these will enter into this environment with no changes to their business concept. The DSO will not change its focus, but possibly revise its standard approach for managing congestions and embrace flexibility. CPOs will continue to serve EV drivers. However, they may differentiate spot-price and subscription fees to honour flexible customers. This flexibility can be sold to other CPOs when opportunities arise. Especially the CPO operators that combine charging services with parking space lease. One exception is the owner of the battery. Currently that issue has not been settled. Most likely the FO itself is going to seize ownership of the battery and use this as a back-up when the ecosystem is too rigid to meet the flexibility demand. But there is still a chance that ownership will be transferred to another party. This battery owner would commit reserve power for peak hours and sign a contract with the FO for this service. However, it might also sell energy directly to the CPOs on an equal basis has those CPOs managing smart charging or V2G. Hence, it will have to compete more directly on price with other stakeholders that can offer flexibility.

6.4.1.5 Potential for scalability

If the ICC proves viable and at least marginally profitable Østfold Energi will bring the concept forward by means of a franchise concept that lends itself well to the concepts presented in D9.4. In Norway there is a growing demand for more, public charging services, charging infrastructure should be extended and ultrafast chargers are wanted by more and more EV drivers. However, analysis of the ICC has shown that ultrafast charging may not be suited in all grid areas without extraordinary measures. That is a business case for the ICC concept and Østfold Energi. At the inception of the first court the general belief is that the concept can be replicated easily. Each court of the ICC type will organize a small ecosystem of CPOs and EV drivers. Multiple courts will constitute an ecosystem at a higher level. As such, some fundamental aspects of the INVADE business model framework has received some empirical support.

6.4.1.6 Contract structure for flexibility

Contract structure has not yet been defined

6.4.1.7 Potential for scalability

If the ICC proves viable and at least marginally profitable Østfold Energi will bring the concept forward by means of a franchise concept that lends itself well to the concepts

presented in D9.4. In Norway there is a growing demand for more, public charging services, charging infrastructure should be extended and ultrafast chargers are wanted by more and more EV drivers. However, analysis of the ICC has shown that ultrafast charging may not be suited in all grid areas without extraordinary measures. That is a business case for the ICC concept and Østfold Energi. At the inception of the first court the general belief is that the concept can be replicated easily. Each court of the ICC type will organize a small ecosystem of CPOs and EV drivers. Multiple courts will constitute an ecosystem at a higher level. As such, some fundamental aspects of the INVADE business model framework has received some empirical support.

6.4.2 The Olsengården housing cooperative case

6.4.2.1 Description

The Olsengården Borettslag, a housing cooperative in Oslo, Norway, is investing in infrastructure upgrades, including rooftop PV, battery storage, and EV chargers. The cooperative needs a solution to handle the dynamic management of their electric loads between these new assets, in combination with the hot water heaters which are shared commonly between the flats. The cooperative wants to explore using the INVADE concepts and platform to operate the infrastructure in the most efficient way, explore additional revenue streams, and gain both visibility through collaborating with the INVADE H2020 project.

6.4.2.2 Case architecture

Figure 36: Olsengården housing cooperative case architecture

6.4.2.3 The Platform-Based Business Model framework applied to this case

PBBM framework works for this case, where Smartly is adopting a platform-based business model and operates a set of local ecosystems. It's difficult, though to consider whether this a set of multiple ecosystems operated by the same player, or rather a global role because their presence is growing towards a national level, and potentially larger.

Figure 37: Olsengården BM framework

6.4.2.4 Business models for relevant stakeholders

1. Energy Service Company + Aggregator: Smartly

Problem <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Residential prosumers need energy management solutions Electricity tariffs based on capacity will lead to high prices for power peaks Investment in energy assets is a high risk investment 	Solution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy management services for multi-tenant buildings Leveraging flexibility in assets to reduce peaks Aggregating multiple customer to access other revenue streams 	Unique Value Proposition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One stop shop for energy services which manages assets and provides financial benefit to operating them in an optimized way. 	Unfair Advantage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct access to assets giving possibility of aggregation and providing services on balancing market and to DSOs 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Housing Cooperatives Housing Cooperative umbrella organizations DSO (eventual) BRP (eventual)
Key Metrics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aggregated flexible controlled asset capacity 			Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct sales to residential customers Complimentary channels from Lyse? Altibox? 	
Cost structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compensation to prosumers for flexibility services (direct or indirect) Financing energy asset investment 			Revenue Streams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subscription contracts with housing cooperatives Long term contract with housing cooperative umbrella organisation Providing flexibility services from aggregated assets (eventual) 	

2. Platform provider: eSmart Systems

Problem <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of standards between different DSOs and BRPs which leads to high integration costs for aggregators Difficult qualification process to participate on some balancing markets 	Solution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Single open API to which different FOs can connect to access revenue streams from DSOs, BRPs, Flexibility markets, etc. 	Unique Value Proposition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Centralization of the integration to various different standards. Integration of data from various different complimentary ecosystems (ex: charging operators, building energy management companies, etc.) 	Unfair Advantage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expertise in integrating and treating large quantities of data for energy management. 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Service Providers and Aggregators (FOs) Charge Point Operators
Key Metrics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aggregated flexible controlled asset capacity 			Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct sales to FOs 	
Cost structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrating new customers, DSOs, etc. Platform maintenance costs, etc. Overhead 			Revenue Streams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SaaS contracts with FOs Fees for computational services High-margin consultancy based on wealth of data 	

Figure 38: Lean canvases in 2 versions for Olsengården

6.4.2.5 Potential for scalability

Similar needs and strategies are required in over 5600 housing cooperatives in Norway, many of which are looking to install or upgrade infrastructure. This model of ownership is a common one in apartments in Norway who have a history of collaborating and sharing strategies in building upgrades. Furthermore, they are part of large umbrella organizations that are eager to roll out innovative concepts to attract new members (ex:

USBL, OBOS). If this exploitation case is replicated in a number of these housing cooperatives and aggregated together, this can lead to asset capacity capable of participating on the balancing market and providing grid support.

6.4.2.6 Contract structure for flexibility

Not yet determined.

6.4.3 The Halden Smart City case

6.4.3.1 Description

The Halden Smart City project is an initiative by the municipality where it replaced the use of its employees’ private cars for work-related travels by a fleet of EVs which it rents during office hours. Outside of office hours, these vehicles are available for rental by private residents. This green mobility solution improves residents’ quality of life in a town where traditional public transit is lacking due to low population. Benefits are economical (lower cost of fleet management), ecological (lower air pollution, reduce purchase of second car), and social (reduced inequality, access for young people, reduced loneliness for seniors, etc.).

6.4.3.2 Case architecture

Figure 39: Halden Smart City case architecture

The fleet of EVs is parked at different charging stations across the city, both in larger charging stations at places like the town hall, mall, hospital as well as distributed in residential neighbourhoods. The **mobility platform provider** communicates with a box

in the vehicles which provides status on location and state of charge, and enables user to unlock the cars through an app. The platform handles booking from users and manages planning and availability of the vehicles.

The rapid deployment of charging infrastructure causes constraints on the local grid points, and the large power peaks when users connect the EVs will lead to high electricity prices under new tariff structures. The municipality, who pays for the electricity of the EV fleet for both employee use and private residents, lacks expertise to plan the infrastructure needs and manage smart charging to avoid high power peaks. For this, an advanced CPO will manage all the municipality’s chargers, where it will interconnect with the mobility platform to receive information on available flexibility from the fleet’s bookings. The advanced CPO will connect to the INVADE platform to obtain optimised charging profiles that take in consideration the DSO’s grid constraints as well as other forecast inputs.

6.4.3.3 The Platform-Based Business Model framework applied to this case

Figure 40: The Halden Smart City case structure

The PBBM presented in D9.4 helps describe the service exchange between the local ecosystem players, including partners like Entur, who manages bookings across different

mobility providers across Norway and WattWorld, who provides shared electric bicycles for the municipal employees. However, to make the service exchange more explicit, it is helpful to specify which service is exchanged, both in value and financial exchange.

In the Halden case, the local ecosystem is built around the Mobility platform, where the management of the charging is handled by the local ecosystem partner (CPO). In turn, the advanced CPO, which is the FO of the case, using the flexibility available from the mobility platform, is not adopting a platform market as defined in [39]. Both the mobility platform and advanced CPO have interesting business models which are described in the following subsection.

6.4.3.4 Business models for relevant stakeholders

1. Mobility platform provider
2. Advanced Charge Point Operator

<p>Problem</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipalities lack expertise in planning and operating EV charger infrastructure High power peaks caused by large number of chargers on a single transformer requires grid upgrades New capacity-based tariffs lead to high electricity costs. 	<p>Solution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Charging as a service to the municipality Smart charging based on the flexibility available in the fleet mobility platform 	<p>Unique Value Proposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Turnkey solution to the municipality to handle all the charging needs Planning and operating charging infrastructure needed for a growing municipal EV fleet Smart charging to accommodate the large fleet in a cost-efficient way 	<p>Unfair Advantage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partnership with mobility platform to access available flexibility for smart charging 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smaller municipalities EV fleet owners and operators
<p>Key Metrics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction of charging power peaks Reduction of grid upgrade and power tariff cost to the municipality 			<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct sales to municipalities 	
<p>Cost structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning and maintaining grid architecture Operating FO platform 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long term contract with municipalities to manage charging as a service 		

Figure 41: Lean Canvas model of the advanced CPO in the Halden case

6.4.3.5 Potential for scalability

This concept has already gathered attention from many municipalities both in Norway and abroad. Cities such as New Delhi and Narvik face similar challenges managing their fleet of vehicles and are attracted by the social benefits incurred by the EV sharing system. The municipality has participated in various international events where others

have been expressing enthusiasm for the project, and the intention to follow up on developments.

The problems in most small-to-medium sized municipalities in Norway are very similar to those in Halden and often lack the expertise to develop and procure the best infrastructure to support their EV fleets. It is likely that a system that is proven functional in Halden will greatly influence the decision making of the other municipalities in the region.

The INVADE platform is well suited to support scalability of the solution if it is rolled out in other municipalities, because it allows for integration of the CPO platforms to a single API, that can manage the compatibility with local DSOs and other stakeholders.

6.4.3.6 Contract structure for flexibility

Not yet determined.

6.4.4 The Jærhagen shopping center case

6.4.4.1 Description

Jærhagen Shopping centre is a fairly large shopping mall with 60 stores, and like similar shopping malls, most of the customers get there by car. The owner of the shopping mall wants to attract customers by offering green and free EV charging.

6.4.4.2 Case architecture

The solar panel installation is generating plenty of energy during the summer, and this energy is distributed to the three 10KWh batteries. The batteries are feeding 30 EV charging stations, each of them able to offer a maximum of 22 KWh charging to the customers.

6.4.4.3 The Platform-Based Business Model framework applied to this case

The solar panels are mainly designed to produce energy for EV charging. When there is more energy than cars charging, the energy is stored in the batteries. If also the batteries are full, the energy is consumed for ventilation, cooling or heating. If there still is more energy, it is fed to the grid according to a prosumer agreement with the DSO.

The battery algorithms are also capable of providing other services and other revenue streams for the customer (the shopping centre).

- Flexibility to the DSO: In a future market, the shopping centre can provide a price for its flexibility to the DSO (and other markets), and when needed, the DSO will choose the lowest bid in the market to free flexibility either by stopping EV charging or discharging of the batteries. This will be done automatically.
- The TSO marketplace for ultrafast frequency acts only seasonally, but provides income to the shopping centre owner for keeping the batteries powered up during some nights - to be able to release this energy if there is a drop in the frequency level.

This model is being used in both residential homes and for commercial customers, but currently the flexibility market is very immature.

6.4.4.4 Potential for scalability

This case has been replicated in several commercial buildings and is supposed to be tested out at airports and harbours during 2020, but charging boats instead of cars.

Figure 42: Advertisement in Norwegian trade journal Teknisk Ukeblad promoting the Jærhagen exploitation case.

6.4.4.5 Contract structure for flexibility

Not yet determined but in process.

7 Discussion

The work we did in D9.4 was to develop a new business model framework that should be able to describe the architecture of the pilot partners business models, as well as facilitating strategic discussions on changing of roles, ecosystem establishment and on transformation from energy to services. We also mapped the pilot owners into concrete business models using the business canvas methodology from Osterwalder as recommended in the DoA.

The current deliverable focuses on validation of the theory put forward in D9.4. The validation examines the relevance of the business model framework and the lean canvas models for the pilot stakeholders. This is studied across interactions with the Exploitation User Group, external stakeholders, pilot-owners and external exploitation cases.

7.1 Value of the business model framework

The feedback we have got from external stakeholders, including the Exploitation User Group, confirms to a great extent that platform-based business models (PBBM) are highly relevant in the future energy market. But the generic business model framework is quite abstract, so it needs to be combined with more concrete business model descriptions, for example using the lean canvas tool.

One addition which makes the framework more useable in a specific context is to define the service exchange between stakeholders, as illustrated in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..** However, there is a limit of what can be described in such a figure without creating complexity that renders it more detrimental than helpful. Another addition that is useful in the context of INVADE, where the focus is to develop business models for battery storages is to locate the ownership and operation of the BESS. A good example of this is in mapping the German pilot in Figure 23.

So, for high level strategic discussions regarding market positioning and the company's new role and direction, the framework is a good tool. And for drilling down in concrete customer value propositions and more, business modelling tools such as the lean canvas tool are important.

7.2 Platform-based business models in energy

The potential of scalable deployment of PBBMs in energy is described in deliverable D9.4, and work has since been performed to verify these affirmations. The external stakeholders consulted were optimistic towards the large potential of these business models but were sceptical towards their deployment in the energy market. The challenge in any market player gaining a dominant global platform position is the first concern mentioned. The second is the highly-regulated nature of the electricity market, where roles are tightly defined and barriers for rapid uptake in these business models are not comparable to the telecom industry. This is a valid argument, but we will argue that as this is true for the grid-part, it is not true behind the meter. And this is exactly where the platform-based business models flourish.

Testing business models in the pilots provides inputs on how different commercial partners are adopting the PBBM framework in their business. The first finding here is that some pilots are better suited than others to embrace the PBBM concepts from D9.4. Those that already have a local ecosystem with existing services towards prosumer/consumers and have prepared for energy-IoT control for customers (e.g. GreenFlux and Smartly) are already applying PBBM concepts and are ideally positioned to take on the local flexibility role.

The German pilot also points to potential opportunities for PBBMs in energy. The first looks at the business for FOs in Germany who operate storages to provide prosumers services to reduce peak tariffs and utilise the flexibility of the assets between peak periods to stack services and access new revenue streams. The pilot also showcased an opportunity to build a PBBM for energy services on top of the SMA backbone. This way, a global player can take on the FO role in a partnership with OEMs like SMA to provide advanced services to improve SMA's control of customer energy assets.

The Spanish had less opportunity to embrace a PBBM in practice. In this case, the pilot is not focusing on the end-user flexibility services and prosumers/consumers, and thus it is not ideal for platform-based business models. We believe this has to do with the fact that PBBM depends on sourcing first, and exploits digital technologies like IoT, AI and Internet distribution to succeed.

The Bulgarian pilot on the other side, can also be characterized as a hybrid, but this time as a hybrid of tangible and in-tangible (ICT-based) flexibility services. Albena's core service is sustainable accommodation and tourism. And they had already many sustainable initiatives like up-cycling of waste, forest protection and more. Now, with the

INVADE project they combine this with increasing the production of renewable energy, controlling load balancing using a battery and water boilers that are upgraded to IoT units and control signals from the INVADE platform. Thus, they now have a hybrid ecosystem of tangible and ICT/IoT based sustainable/renewable services which is unique in the European accommodation/tourism market. It still remains to see whether they will exploit this new business opportunity.

7.3 Business models for flexibility operators

The flexibility operator as defined in deliverable D4.1 is an independent role that can offer its flexibility services to end-users, BRPs or grid operators. In business terms, there are different ways this role can be adopted by stakeholders in the market. Deliverable D9.4 divides the FO into two distinct categories: operating behind the meter (prosumer services), and trading with other market actors (DSOs and BRPs).

Gathering feedback from external stakeholders, the first validation step stated in section **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, showed an interpretation closely aligned with the theory presented.

Lastly, there is concern of the independence of a FO that serves as trading intermediary between market actors was signalled as a necessity. On one hand, this impacts the ownership of the FO platform, which should be independent from biased stakeholders, and regulation defining the role in the electricity market. This provides support for the necessity of dividing FOs between the local and global roles, where a global flexibility operator should be regulated to provide unbiased signals to different market players.

The external stakeholders were also presented the concept of **flexibility operator**, and they all acknowledged this role and concept. The sceptics emphasized the importance of having a neutral FO, and as the majority of the stakeholder group believed that the retailers would take the FO-role, this directly contradicts the neutral part of such a role.

We believe that the role will naturally be divided into a local and global role, where the local flexibility role will not be regulated at all, whereas the more dominant global flexibility role has a higher probability to become regulated or neutral.

7.4 eSmart Systems

eSmart is responsible for developing the central part of the Integrated INVADE Platform (IIP), and one could easily conclude that they would seek to take the global flexibility role.

But this is not the case, even if they have supported some of the pilots where there are no local flexibility operator like Bulgaria. For other pilots they take the role as a global service provider and provides them with machine learning optimized time and control series of data. This is the case for the Norwegian, German and Dutch pilots. However, eSmart made it clear in the Copenhagen meeting in September that their ambition is to licence FO-software. We believe they have a great opportunity to play a bigger role, but this a decision that lies in the hands of their board. WP3 have worked with the management in eSmart, so their original role-ambition might change. This is well described in D3.6.

Regarding the exploitation cases, we see that they either establish a PBBM or they will be a part of ecosystems. We have to emphasise that both the internal and external exploitation cases are all at very early stages, so our discussion here is premature but still valuable.

Jærhagen as an exploitation case has been established during the early phase of the INVADE-project by eSmart and Smartly respectively. This is a clear indication that medium and large business customers are the first market ripe for flexibility services. For Smartly this also indicates a small industrial shift from the multi-tenant market to the business market. Towards the end of the project they started to advertise their solution in the market. Here, Smartly holds its position as local flexibility operator and local ecosystem manager, and Jærhagen is a large and advanced prosumer.

Another interesting move to observe is Smartly's industrial shift towards the SMB market which was launched at the end of 2019, where part of its local INVADE platform is reused and adjusted in another market. This is similar to what Uber did when extending its value proposition from transporting people to transport food.

The exploitation case of Inspiria charging court use a PBBM with both a downstream and upstream part of the business model covered. According to Cambridge university's definition of a PBBM, there needs to be more than just an exchange-function for one service. We believe this is the case because in addition to this local flexibility market, you also find services like parking and local energy production. And is likely that other services will emerge in this local marketplace.

If we look at the Olsengården exploitation case we see a clear PBBM with project partners being ecosystem partners. Smartly could here replicate the local ecosystem solution they have already installed in Solvang BRL in Stavanger (multi-tenant building with PV, batteries and smart EV-charging). Again, which role eSmart wants to take here

is still under evaluation. Schneider is a technology and energy-IoT ecosystem partner, taking a more comprehensive role than at Solvang BRL as they deliver all the devices.

7.5 Business models for batteries

Studying the battery market, it is interesting to see how it plays out related to the German regulatory framework. A set of services that exploits the same battery solution emerges. Batteries must be modular in the sense that they can be sliced up to support different use-cases (business cases).

Examples of different services from the same battery are:

1. Peak shaving
2. Support EV shaving for a business customer to save infrastructure cost for upgrading.
3. Emergency (back-up) service
4. Reducing energy cost through trading in low-cost periods between transients.

Examples of different services in the upstream market are:

1. Balancing (ancillary) market. However, the barrier for entering this market is very high (strong requirements for certification, and one fault and you are out)
2. Power exchange market (trading with flexibility market)
3. Helping the DSO in stressed grid situations
4. Self sufficiency

One example of the certification risk is Enfo, which made one error towards Statnett, and were thrown out of the market. Eventually the company went out of business. Another observation from the Norwegian market is that some producers are looking at PV-generated electricity to save the valuable water resources in the dams.

When it comes to the concept of V2X, the EUG is sceptical as to whether this service will have a profound impact in the future energy market. Only half of the group believe that V2X will have impact, and this is mainly due to high cost, unclear regulation and little traction from the car manufacturers. The last point can be confirmed, as the INVADE pilot partners have struggled to get V2G equipment at all.

8 Conclusion

According to the DoA of the INVADE project the business model work should focus on the new strong trends in the energy market. They can be summarized in two main categories; customer centricity and digitalization. On the customer side both decentralisation and sharing economy trends are strong, and they go in parallel with strong customer centric regulation in the EU. On the digitalization side, we find that not only do we have many digital technology trends like IoT, AI and cloud, but we also find new business models that feed on the exponential growth mechanisms provided by digital technologies.

So, following a state-of-the-art review of business models, platform-based business models (PBBM) has been the focal point of the work in WP9. This choice has also been fuelled by the fact that whereas Europe has a strong role in technology innovation, we are lagging far behind when it comes to establishing platform-based companies.

The work has been divided into four phases: exploration, development, validation and exploitation. Our conclusions can be summarized as follows:

- Platform based business models are relevant in the energy market. This is confirmed both by the Exploitation User Group, external stakeholders, as well as with the majority of our pilot owners. But most of all we can see these new actors emerging in the market.
- Platform-based business models fit well with introducing flexibility services in the market. However, there is a clear distinction between a pure exchange role of one service versus a platform role, as the latter typically has an ecosystem and more services in the market.
- We see a clear pattern related to market entry for flexibility. The recommended order should be:
 - 1 Start with a core service that enables control of the flexibility sources like smart EV-chargers, PV, smart home, batteries, thermal heaters.
 - 2 Then enter the most mature market first where we find effect-based tariffs, typically medium to large companies and multi-tenant buildings. And introduce end-user flexibility services. Here, financing from the local ecosystem can accelerate sourcing.

3 Do industrial shifts towards neighbouring markets/branches to increase sourcing.

4 Start doing up-stream flexibility trading and aggregation when regulation allows DSOs to participate.

- The flexibility role will typically be divided between two main entities; the local flexibility operator controlling energy-IoT assets and end customers, and the global flexibility operator doing the more difficult trading and providing the market place for flexibility.
- The global flexibility operator should start in national markets where regulatory barriers for the DSOs are removed first. Today, the regulation for DSOs favours investing in new infrastructure only, and not flexibility trading. This must be changed in order for an upstream market to be established.
- Despite a dramatic drop in price of batteries, all the pilots claim that a one-service approach is not feasible. You will need to stack more services on a battery. An example is peak shaving for EVs, emergency functions and increased self-consumption at the customer side.
- Simplification for end-customers should be a big part of the value proposition, and simplification can range from user interaction and billing to reducing the number of gateways/apps. And removing customer pain points.
- Providing flexibility services using platform-based business models is feasible in ensuring sourcing of flexibility assets. This will in turn result in network effects that accelerate growth.
- Platform-based business models do not fit all our pilot partners, especially those that do not focus on the end-users.
- We see that the INVADE business model framework support the idea of a global consolidating role of DSOs and local ecosystems, thus becoming one column in EUs Digital Single Market for big data.
- The INVADE business model framework is applicable in particular to enable strategic discussions in companies regarding roles, to transform from a value chain to a value network company with ecosystems and partners, and finally to change mindset from energy to services.

The global flexibility role is yet to be taken. However, taking this platform position will require investments at a level we rarely see in Europe today. This is an important

part of the reason why US and Asia based companies are taking these global positions in other industries. And as the platform-based business models have an inherent feature of “winner takes all”, it is advisable that the European Commission ceases this chance to conquer this global market position as part of its journey towards EUs Digital Single Market for Big Data.

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